

Kinetics of Oxidation of Benzene azodimethylaniline and Methyl Orange by Chromic Acid in Presence of 1,10-Phenanthroline and 2,2'-Bipyridyl

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The title reaction studied spectrophotometrically was found to be first order with respect to both the reactants. The reaction is catalysed by H^+ ion and the order with respect to H^+ ion was found to be unity in both the cases. 1,10-Phenanthroline was found to have greater catalytic effect than 2,2'-bipyridyl and a plot of $1/k_1$ vs $1/[\text{phen}]$ was a straight line with a positive slope and intercept on $1/k_1$ -axis, whereas a plot of $1/k_1$ vs $1/[\text{bipy}]$ was also a straight line but passing through the origin. A decrease in the activation energies was observed when compared to that of uncatalysed reaction and the decrease was more in the case of 1,10-phenanthroline-catalysed reaction than that of 2,2'-bipyridyl-catalysed one. Plausible mechanism has been proposed to explain the catalytic behaviour of these ligands.

THE accelerating effects of 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl on chromium(VI) oxidations were known for a long time¹. The accelerating effects of these ligands on chromium(VI) oxidations were explained by postulating that these ligands stabilise the transition state and also the intermediate oxidation states of chromium. However, no systematic kinetic investigation of this accelerating effect on chromic acid oxidations has been, so far, reported. With a view to having a clear insight into the mechanism of catalysis of chromic acid oxidations by these ligands, the present authors have taken up a detailed kinetic study of oxidation of benzene azodimethylaniline (BADMA) and methyl orange (*p*-SO₃H BADMA) by chromic acid in the presence of 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl. Michaelis type of kinetics was observed with 1,10-phenanthroline as catalyst but not in the case of 2,2'-bipyridyl used as catalyst. Interestingly, Michaelis type of kinetics is very rarely observed in chromic acid oxidations.

Experimental

Double-distilled water was used for the preparation of all solutions. E. Merck 'pro analysi' chromium trioxide was used for the preparation of chromium(VI) solution and it was standardised by the improved iodometric method². BADMA was prepared by the reported method³ and its solution in 5% acetic acid was standardised with standard titanous chloride solution⁴. Perchloric acid and 1,10-phenanthroline (both E. Merck, pro analysi) and 2,2'-bipyridyl (AnalaR) were used. Sodium perchlorate solution was prepared by neutralising requisite

quantity of standard perchloric acid solution with standard sodium hydroxide solution.

The experiments were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions by isolating the aromatic azo compound and the course of reaction was followed by measuring the optical density of the unreacted azo compound at 510 nm. Temperature of the reaction mixture was maintained constant to $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The rate constants were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The stoichiometry of the reaction in the presence and absence of 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl was found to be 4 moles of chromium(VI) to 3 moles of azo compound. In agreement with the stoichiometric results, the oxidation product was found to be the corresponding nitroso compound as evidenced by the spot test⁵. Under the experimental conditions employed by the present authors, the extent of the uncatalysed reaction was negligible. Hence, no correction due to uncatalysed reaction was made in calculating the rate constants for the catalysed reaction.

Results and Discussion

The order with respect to each of the azo compounds is unity as revealed by the straight line graphs obtained at different initial concentrations of each of the azo compounds for $\log(O.D.)$ vs time plots, and they were found to be parallel to each other (Table 1). The order with respect to chromium(VI) is unity as revealed by the straight lines obtained passing through origin when k_1 was

plotted against $[Cr^{VI}]$ (Table 2) Plots of k_1 vs concentration of hydrogen ion was straight line passing through the origin in each showing that the reaction is of first order with respect to hydrogen ion. These results are presented in Table 3.

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON CONCENTRATION OF SUBSTRATE

$[Phen] = 8.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[Bipy] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[HClO_4] = 0.1 M$, $\mu = 0.5$, Acetic acid = 3% (v/v), Temp. = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$, $[Cr^{VI}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ when Phen used and is $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ when Bipy used as ligand.

[Substrate] $\times 10^3 M$	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k'_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$
0.51 ^a	3.68	3.74
0.56	3.35	3.52
0.64	3.74	3.72
0.74	3.41	3.51
0.99	3.70	3.74
1.11	3.38	3.52
1.65	3.72	3.76
1.85	3.35	3.54

^aBipy used as ligand
BADMA as substrate.
^bMethyl orange as substrate.

TABLE 2—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON CONCENTRATION OF CHROMIUM(VI)

$[Methyl\ orange] = 0.99 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[BADMA] = 1.11 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[HClO_4] = 0.1 M$, $[Phen] = 8.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $\mu = 0.5$, Acetic acid = 3% (v/v), Temp = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$, $[Bipy] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$.

$Cr^{VI} \times 10^4 M$	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k'_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k_2 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k'_2 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$
1.0	3.70	3.38	2.12	1.55
1.5	5.02	4.55	—	—
2.0	7.05	6.41	3.74	3.52
2.5	8.91	7.98	—	—
3.0	10.42	9.45	5.92	5.21
3.5	12.10	11.34	—	—
4.0	14.24	12.96	7.30	7.12
5.0	—	—	9.42	8.44
6.0	—	—	11.23	10.57

k_1 and k'_1 = Pseudo-first order rate constants when Phen used as ligand.

k_2 and k'_2 = Pseudo-first order rate constants when Bipy used as ligand.

k_1 and k_2 = Pseudo-first order rate constants when methyl orange used as substrate.

k_1 and k'_2 = Pseudo-first order rate constants when BADMA used as substrate.

TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON HYDROGEN ION CONCENTRATION

$[Methyl\ orange] = 0.99 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[BADMA] = 1.11 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Phen] = 8.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $\mu = 0.5$, Acetic acid = 3% (v/v), Temp. = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$, $[Bipy] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Cr^{VI}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ when Phen used as ligand and is $2.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ when Bipy used as ligand.

$[HClO_4] M$	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k'_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k_2 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k'_2 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$
0.1	3.70	3.38	3.74	3.52
0.2	6.63	6.34	7.52	6.68
0.3	10.86	9.71	11.48	8.95
0.4	14.07	12.52	14.81	14.10
0.5	17.36	15.96	18.72	17.50

k_1, k'_1, k_2, k'_2 , defined as in Table 2.

Effect of varying ligand: The pseudo-first order rate constant (k_1) was determined at different initial concentrations of 1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridyl, keeping the concentrations of all other reactants constant. While the plot of k_1 vs $[2,2'$ -bipyridyl] is a straight line passing through origin at all concentrations employed (Table 4), the plot of k_1 vs $[phen]$ is linear only at lower

Fig. 1. Plots of $1/k_1$ vs $1/[Phen]$; $[Cr^{VI}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[Methyl\ orange] = 0.99 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[HClO_4] = 0.1 M$, $\mu = 0.5$.

Fig. 2. Plots of $1/k_1$ vs $1/[Phen]$; $[Cr^{VI}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[BADMA] = 1.11 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[HClO_4] = 0.1 M$, $\mu = 0.5$.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF VARYING THE CONCENTRATION OF BIPYRIDYL ON RATE

[Cr^{V2+}] = 2.0 × 10⁻⁴ M, [Methyl orange] = 0.99 × 10⁻⁵ M, [BADMA] = 1.11 × 10⁻⁵ M, [HClO₄] = 0.1 M, μ = 0.5, Acetic acid = 3% (v/v), Temp. = 25 ± 0.1°.

[Bipy] × 10 ³ M	k ₁ * × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	k ₁ ** × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
2.0	3.74	3.52
3.0	5.97	5.05
4.0	7.05	6.98
5.0	8.83	9.10
6.0	10.50	10.31
7.0	12.48	12.42

*Methyl orange used as substrate.

**BADMA used as substrate.

1,10-phenanthroline concentrations. At higher concentrations of the ligand, curvature was observed showing a definite trend towards the attainment of limiting rate at still higher concentrations of 1,10-phenanthroline. Further, a plot of 1/k₁ vs 1/[Phen] is a straight line with a definite positive intercept on 1/k₁-axis (Figs. 1 and 2). Ionic strength was found to have negligible effect on the rate of the reaction.

The dependence of rate on the concentrations of Cr^{V2+}, the substrate and 1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridyl suggests their participation in the transition state. The authors believe that Cr^{V2+} forms, in a preequilibrium, a 1:1 complex with 2,2'-bipyridyl or 1,10-phenanthroline which acts as a more powerful oxidising species than the uncomplexed Cr^{V2+}. Such complexes were reported earlier with pyridine and 1,10-phenanthroline by Sisler *et al.*^{6,7}. The complex in the subsequent rate-determining step oxidises the aromatic azo compounds forming Cr^{IV}L. Cr^{IV}L is reduced to Cr^{III}L in fast steps. The detailed schematic mechanism is given in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

The rate law from Scheme 1 is represented as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -d[\text{Ar}-\text{N}=\text{N}-\text{Ar}']/dt \\
 & = \frac{k K_1 [\text{HCrO}_4^-] [\text{L}] [\text{H}^+] [\text{ArN}=\text{N}-\text{Ar}']}{1 + K_1 [\text{L}]} \quad (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$k_1 = \frac{k K_1 [\text{HCrO}_4^-] [\text{L}] [\text{H}^+]}{1 + K_1 [\text{L}]}, \text{ when } [\text{HCrO}_4^-] \gg [\text{ArN}=\text{N}-\text{Ar}'] \quad (2)$$

$$1/k_1 = \frac{1}{k K_1 [\text{Cr}^{\text{V}2+}] [\text{L}] [\text{H}^+]} + \frac{1}{k [\text{Cr}^{\text{V}2+}] [\text{H}^+]} \quad (3)$$

From the equation (2) plots of 1/k₁ vs 1/[L] must be straight lines with positive intercepts on 1/k₁-axes. The authors believe that an obtainment of intercept in the case of 1,10-phenanthroline and its absence in the case of 2,2'-bipyridyl-catalysed reaction can be explained by assuming that the stability constant in the former case has appreciable magnitude and the equation (2) is obeyed. But in the case of bipyridyl-catalysed reaction, the stability constant may be small in magnitude and the product K₁ [L] may be negligible in comparison with one in the denominator of the right-hand side of equation (1). Consequently, the plot of 1/k₁ vs 1/[L] will be a straight line passing through origin in the case of bipyridyl-catalysed reaction. It is interesting to note that 1,10-phenanthroline, in general, forms stronger complexes with metal ions than bipyridyl⁸.

The authors consider that the higher rates observed in the presence of 1,10-phenanthroline may be due to the greater stabilisation of transition state involving Cr^{V2+}, ligand and substrate. 1,10-Phenanthroline which forms stronger complex is likely to stabilise the transition state more, leading to greater acceleration. This may be due to the presence of a better π-electron system in 1,10-phenanthroline than in 2,2'-bipyridyl. The rate acceleration may also be due to the stabilisation of Cr^{IV} by these ligands.

Activation parameters: The data of the activation energy calculated for the reaction are presented in Tables 5 and 6. The data of the uncatalysed reaction are presented in Table 7. The data clearly show that the catalysed reaction has lower activation energy than the uncatalysed reaction and the decrease in the activation energy is greater in the case of 1,10-phenanthroline-catalysed reaction

TABLE 5—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS WITH LIGAND AS 1,10-PHENANTHROLINE

Temp. (± 0.1)°C	k* × 10 ⁻⁴ l ² mol ⁻² min ⁻¹	E _a (± 0.3) kcal mol ⁻¹	k'** × 10 ⁻⁴ l ² mol ⁻² min ⁻¹	E' _a (± 0.3) kcal mol ⁻¹
25	5.00		4.40	
30	5.32	2.20	4.75	2.80
35	5.64		5.13	

* Methyl orange used as substrate.

** BADMA used as substrate.

TABLE 6—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS WITH LIGAND AS 2,2'-BIPYRIDYL

Temp. (± 0.1)°C	k^* $\times 10^{-3}$ $l^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$	$E_a(\pm 0.5)$ kcal mol^{-1}	k'^{**} $\times 10^{-3}$ $l^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$	$E_a(\pm 0.5)$ kcal mol^{-1}
25	1.87	4.0	1.76	4.2
30	2.09		1.98	
35	2.59		2.48	

* and ** As in Table 5.

TABLE 7—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR UNCATALYSED REACTION

[Cr^{VI}] = $6.82 \times 10^{-4} M$, [HClO₄] = 2.0M, $\mu = 2.0$, Acetic acid = 40% (v/v), Substrate = BADMA

Temp. (± 0.1)°C	k_1 $\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	E_a (± 1.0) kcal mol^{-1}
30.5	30.23	10.0
35.0	38.86	
40.0	46.06	

TABLE 8—VALUE OF STABILITY CONSTANT AND ITS ENTHALPY FOR CHROMIUM(VI)-1,10-PHENANTHROLINE COMPLEX

Temp. °C	k_1 $\times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	ΔH (± 0.5) kcal mol^{-1}
25	10.45	- 4.80
30	9.13	
35	8.01	

showing that the ligand stabilises the transition state more than the bipyridyl ligand. From the slopes and intercepts of the plots of $1/k_1$ vs $1/[\text{Phen}]$ the authors calculated the values of the stability constants for chromium(VI)-1,10-phenanthroline complex at three temperatures. Using these data, the enthalpy of formation ΔH of Cr^{VI}L was calculated from the integrated expression of Van't Hoff (Table 8).

References

1. S. V. ANANTHA KRISHNAN and H. JAYARAMAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 146; S. V. ANANTHA KRISHNAN and R. V. VARADARAJAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 423; V. M. SADAGOPARAMANUJAM, S. SUNDARAM and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAM, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 889.
2. G. GOPALA RAO and C. R. VISWANATHAM, *Curr. Sci.*, 1942, 11, 102.
3. A. I. VOGEL, "Elementary Practical Organic Chemistry", Quantitative Organic Analysis, Longmans Green, London, 1971, Part III, p. 754.
4. A. I. VOGEL, "Practical Organic Chemistry", ELBS, London, 1968, p. 265.
5. F. FEIGL, "Spot tests in Organic Analysis", Elsevier, New York, 1966, p. 290.
6. H. H. SISLER, J. D. BUSH and O. E. ACCOUNTIUS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3827; H. H. SISLER, W. C. L. MING, E. METTER and F. R. HURLEY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 446; O. E. ACCOUNTIUS, J. D. BUSH and H. H. SISLER, *Inorg. Synth.*, 1953, 4, 94.
7. H. H. SISLER, N. EL-JADIR and D. H. BUSCH, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, 16, 257.
8. H. IRWING and D. H. MELLOR, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 5222.